

Palaeographical Development of the Brāhmī Script in Ceylon from 3rd B.C. to 7th A.C.

THE material from which the accompanying chart has been compiled consists of 72 published (28 without Plates) and 97 unpublished inscriptions which fall into two categories, (A) inscriptions which can be dated from the identities of the Kings named in them, and (B) a few, undated inscriptions whose script so closely approximates to that of the dated inscriptions that they could safely be used to supply missing letters. A full list of these inscriptions is given below :—

3rd B.C. Category (A)

Devānampiya Tissa.—(1) Mihintalē inscription. A.S.C.A.R.¹ 1911-12, page 94, Cave No. 2, revised*; (2) 2 unpublished inscriptions at Piccandiyāva. A.I.C.² 84*; (3) unpublished inscription at Kolladeniya. A.S.C.A.R. 1934, para 71(1)*.

Uttiya.—(1) 3 unpublished inscriptions at Mihintalē. A.S.C.A.R. 1933, paras 53 and 54.

2nd B.C.

Dutthagāmaṇi Abhaya.—(1) Unpublished inscription at Kusalānakanda†; (2) unpublished inscription at Kaluḍupotana-malai. A.S.C.A.R. 1933, para 84†; (3) 14 unpublished inscriptions at Koṭṭadāmuhele. A.S.C.A.R. 1934, para 78*; (4) unpublished inscription at Dambulla*; (5) unpublished inscription at Koravakgala*. A.S.C.A.R. 1934, para 71 (ii); (6) unpublished inscription at Silavakanda. A.S.C.A.R. 1935, para 41*; (7) inscription at Kossagamakanda. J.R.A.S. (C.B.)³, Vol. 36, No. 98*; (8) Tōnigala inscriptions. A.I.C. 1, revised*; (9) unpublished inscription at Jahapagama. A.S.C.A.R. 1933, para 56*; (10) 2 inscriptions at Mihintalē. A.S.C.A.R. 1911-12, page 96, Cave No. 13, and page 97, Cave No. 23, revised*.

Saddhā Tissa.—(1) 5 unpublished inscriptions at Rājagala. A.S.C.A.R. 1935, para 39*; (2) Dambulla inscription. A.I.C. 3, revised*; (3) Vālaellugodakanda inscriptions. A.S.C.A.R. 1940-45, Plate 14*; (4) Mihintalē

* The identification of the King is probable, but not certain.

† Inscription of a Ruler of Rohaṇa, probably prior to Dutthagāmaṇi Abhaya.

1. Archaeological Survey of Ceylon, Annual Report.

2. Müller: Ancient Inscriptions of Ceylon.

3. Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society Ceylon Branch.

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inscription. A.S.C.A.R. 1911-12, page 97, Cave No. 25, revised*; (5) unpublished inscription at Nuvaragala*.

Lañjalissa.—(1) E.Z. I., Plate 18, No. 1.

1st Half of 1st B.C.

Vattagāmaṇi Abhaya.—(1) 11 inscriptions at Gallena. A.I.C. 2; A.S.C.A.R. 1935, Para 40*; (2) unpublished inscription at Sassēruva*; (3) 3 inscriptions at Nuvarakanda. C.J.S.⁵ II. 126, Nos. 529, 530 and 532; (4) unpublished inscription at Kumburuleṇa*; (5) E.Z. I, Plate 19, No. 3.

Mahācūḷī Mahātissa.—(1) unpublished inscription at Koravakgala. A.S.C.A.R. 1934, para 71 (iii); (2) Demada Oya inscription. J.R.A.S. (C.B.), Vol. 36, No. 98.

2nd Half of 1st B.C.

Kuṭakaṇṇa Tissa.—(1) unpublished inscription at Mihintalē; (2) Mīnvila inscription. E.Z. III, 156, note 5.

Bhātikābhaya.—(1) Mihintalē inscription. A.I.C. 20, revised; (2) Dunumaḍalakanda inscription. A.I.C. 15, revised; (3) Galgirikanda inscription. A.I.C. 17; (4) unpublished inscription at Tirappanakaḍavala; (5) Mōlāhiṭiyavelēgala inscription. C.A. III, Plate 13; E.Z. III, 154; (6) Kirinda inscription. J.R.A.S. (C.B.), Vol. 36, No. 98*; (7) Tissamahārāma inscription. J.R.A.S. (C.B.), Vol. 36, No. 98*.

1st Half of 1st A.C.

Mahādāṭhika Mahānāga.—(1) Mōlāhiṭiyavelēgala inscription. C.A. III, Plate 13; E.Z. III, 155; (2) E.Z. I, Plate 13 (Maha Ratmalē); (3) unpublished inscription at Rātravala. A.S.C.A.R. 1934, para 71 (iv); (4) unpublished inscription at "Line" malai; (5) unpublished inscription at Vehera-uda-malai. A.S.C.A.R. 1935, para 43; (6) unpublished inscription at Diyabāṭṭa. A.I.C. 48; (7) unpublished inscription at Kaduruvāva*; (8) unpublished inscription at Billavagala; (9) Koṭaveheragala inscription. C.A. III, Plate 19, No. 1.

2nd Half of 1st A.C.

Amaṇḍagāmaṇi Abhaya.—(1) Gōnavatta inscription. C.J.S. II, 150, note 1†; (2) unpublished Ridī Vihāra inscription. C.J.S. II, 179; (3) unpublished Hātigamuva inscription. C.J.S. II, 126, No. 525.

Subha.—(1) E.Z. III, Plate 13.

4. Epigraphia Zeylanica.

5. Ceylon Journal of Science Section G.

* The identification of the King is probable, but not certain.

† The primitive letter-forms appearing in the Chart during this period all occur in this inscription.

Vasabha.—(1) Perumaiyan-kulam inscription. E.Z. I, Plate 13; (2) unpublished inscription at Kūmacōlai; (3) unpublished inscription at Sina-diyagala; (4) Vallipuram Gold Plate. E.Z. IV, Plate 23; (5) unpublished inscription at Maḍavala. C.J.S. II, 211, No. 657; (6) 2 unpublished inscriptions at Sandagiri Vehera. C.J.S. II, 25, Nos. 399 and 400; (7) unpublished inscription at Andaravāva; (8) inscription at Alut Hammillāva. A.S.C. 7th Report, 66.

1st Half of 2nd A.C.

Vañkanāsika Tissa.—(1) unpublished inscription at Kāḍigala. C.J.S. II, 123, No. 510; (2) unpublished inscription at Tammanāva. A.S.C.A.R. 1935, para 43; (3) Habāssa inscription. E.Z. IV, Plate 22.

Gajabāhuka Gāmaṇi.—(1) Ruvanvālisāya inscription. A.I.C. 5, revised; (2) unpublished inscription at Ratanapāsāda; (3) Vilēvāva inscription. A.S.C. 7th Report, 58; (4) Tāmaragala inscription. A.I.C. 12, revised; (5) unpublished inscription at Situlpavva. A.S.C.A.R. 1934, para 71 (vi); (6) E.Z. I, Plate 27; (7) E.Z. III, Plate 7; (8) unpublished inscription at Periyakaḍu Vihāra. C.J.S. II, 215, No. 675; (9) unpublished inscription at Mīnvila; (10) unpublished inscription at Tambalagollāva; (11) Vihāregala inscription. E.Z. III, Plate 13; (12) unpublished inscription at Māvila; (13) unpublished inscription at Goḍavāya. C.J.S. II, 197, No. 586.

Mahallaka Nāga.—(1) Timbirivāva inscription. A.S.C. 7th Report, 55, No. 2; (2) Tammanakanda inscription. A.S.C. 7th Report, 47, No. 2; (3) unpublished inscription at Mīnvila; (4) unpublished inscription at Sōmāvatiya. A.S.C.A.R. 1939, para 29.

Bhātikatissa.—(1) unpublished inscription at Ganēkanda; (2) unpublished inscription at Pahala Usgollāva.

2nd Half of 2nd A.C.

Kanitha Tissa.—(1) unpublished inscription at Anurādhapura; (2) Situlpauva inscription. A.I.C. 16, revised; (3) Occāpukallu inscription. Parker 444; J.R.A.S. (C.B.), Vol. 28, page 55; (4) Abhayagiri Relic Caskets. C.J.S. II, 201, Nos. 610 and 611; (5) 2 unpublished inscriptions at "Line" malai; (6) unpublished inscription at Nelugala; (7) Tammanakanda inscription. A.S.C. 7th Report, 47, No. 3; (8) unpublished inscription at Nelumpat Pokuṇa. A.S.C.A.R. 1934, para 71 (vii).

Sirināga I.—(1) unpublished inscription at Periyakaḍu vihāra. C.J.S. II, 215, No. 676.

3rd A.C.

Sirināga II.—(1) Vessagiriya inscription. E.Z. IV, Plate 22; (2) Timbirivāva inscription. A.S.C. 7th Report, 55.

Goṭhābhaya.—(1) Timbirivāva inscription. E.Z. IV, Plate 22.

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Mahāsena.—(1) unpublished inscription at Likolavāva ; (2) Jetavanārāma inscription. E.Z. IV, Plate 27.

4th A.C.

Sirimeghavaṇṇa.—(1) 2 inscriptions at Tōnigala. E.Z. III, Plate 14; E.Z. III, 172, note 2; (2) 3 unpublished inscriptions at Nā-maḷuva; (3) 2 unpublished inscriptions at Deberahela; (4) Debelgala inscription. A.S.C. 7th Report, 50, No. 3, revised; (5) unpublished inscription at Pokuṇuviṭa. A.S.C.A.R. 1931, page 5; (6) Rūgam inscription. A.I.C. 24, revised; (7) unpublished inscription at Kārambagala. A.I.C. 21 (a); E.Z. III, 179, note 3; (8) unpublished inscription at Maṇḍagala.

Jettihatissa II.—(1) Velangolla inscription. A.I.C. 102, revised C.J.S. II, 126, No. 524; (2) 2 unpublished inscriptions at Bōvattagala. A.S.C.A.R. 1934, para 71 (viii).

Buddhadāsa.—(1) Ruvanvālisāya inscription. E.Z. III, Plate 8; (2) Vēragoḍagala inscription. C.A. III, Plate 20.

Uṇṇatissa I.—(1) unpublished inscription at Pānāma. C.J.S. II, 113, No. 457.

5th A.C.

Mahanāma.—(1) Vēragoḍagala inscription. C.A. III, Plate 20; (2) Tissamahārāma inscription. A.I.C. 67, revised.

Khudda Pārinda.—(1) Anurādhapura inscription. E.Z. IV, Plate II.

Dāṭhiya.—(1) Kataragama inscription. E.Z. III, Plate 23.

6th A.C.

Kumārādāsa.—(1) Nāgirikanda inscription. E.Z. IV, Plate II.

Moggallāna II.—(1) Nilagama inscription. E.Z. IV, Plate 28.

7th A.C.

Vahaka Maharaja†.—(1) Veherakema inscription. E.Z. IV, Plate 14, No. 1.

2nd B.C.

Category (B)

(1) unpublished inscription at Sīlavakanda. Letter, Gha; (2) unpublished inscription at Koravakgala. Letters, Kha, Cha and Tha; (3) Nāṭṭunkanda inscription. A.S.C. 7th Report, 48, No. 2. Letter, E; (4) unpublished inscription at Kaṇṇitavimalai. C.J.S. II, 118, No. 481. Letter, Ḍa.

1st Half of 1st B.C.

(1) 2 unpublished inscriptions at Handagala. Letters, E, Gha and Ḍa; (2) unpublished inscription at Monerāgala. Letters, Kha, Dha and Tha; (3) unpublished inscription at Koravakgala. Letter, O.

† This King is not mentioned in the Chronicles.

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2nd Half of 1st B.C.

(1) unpublished inscription at Bambaragastalāva. Letter, Gha; (2) unpublished inscription at Āṇḍiyagala. Letters, Kha, Bha.

1st Half of 1st A.C.

(1) unpublished inscription at Billavagala. Letter, Cha.

2nd Half of 2nd A.C.

(1) Habarana inscription. A.I.C. 61, revised. Letters, Bha, Ṇa and Na.

5th to 7th A.C.

(1) Diyagama inscription. A.I.C. 85, revised. Letters, I, Ja, Ha and I.a; (2) chart at E.Z. IV, Plate 15. All letters.

The chronology adopted is (i) up to the reign of Mahāsenā, the chronology of kings appearing at the end of Dr. G. C. Mendis' paper on "The Chronology of the Early Pāli Chronicles" in the *University of Ceylon Review*, Volume V. No. 1, page 39, (ii) the period 302 A.C. to 409 A.C. for the first four Kings of the *Cūlavamsa* and (iii) thereafter, Geiger's chronology.

I am very greatly indebted to Dr. S. Paranavitana, the Archaeological Commissioner, who very kindly permitted me to examine and copy the estampages of many unpublished inscriptions. Where no estampages exist, I have had to rely on my own eye-copies and photographs.

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